

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP6 – Cross-stakeholder engagement, endorsement and adoption

D6.5 Recommendations for a sustainable information production, dissemination and engagement ecosystem

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Abstract

This deliverable reports on the engagement with a stakeholder community to guide the scaling up and sustaining an online information resource for women regarding the latest evidence on the safety of medicines use during pregnancy. This sustainable result from the Innovative Medicines Initiative ConcePTION project has been considered to be the most viable result for which a multi-stakeholder advisory and promoting community could be of value, within the scope of work package 6 to foster.

The online information portal, known as MUMS (Mothers using Medicines Safely), provides lay summaries of the current evidence about the safety of specific medicines when used during pregnancy and breastfeeding. MUMS has been developed within ConcePTION on the basis of well researched user needs and requirements, as a fully implemented web portal, also suitable for mobile device access. It currently has illustrative content comprising around 40 medicines of high frequency use, developed through a formal and documented editorial and governance process. Lareb, one of the collaborators in the project, has agreed to take over the governance and operation of MUMS after the IMI project ends.

MUMS will be offered free for use by women of childbearing age and any other members of the public. It is recognised that health professionals may also find this information useful, and might direct their patients to it. It will be targeted at countries and languages that do not already have a trusted national online resource for this information, which would usually be provided by a Teratology Information Service centre, occasionally by regulatory or HTA agencies. Many countries, including in Europe, do not have such centres, or have centres that have the expertise but not the resources to develop, provide and maintain up to date medicines safety evidence for the public in their country.

However, funding will be required to widen the medicines coverage, translate the lay summaries into multiple languages, to maintain and update the existing content and to comprehensively promote the resource in local language through trustworthy organisations within target countries (to be agreed). The material in this deliverable presents the rationale behind, design of and value of the MUMS resource to women across Europe. Chapter 4 was prepared to inform and structure discussion at a multi-stakeholder event focused on MUMS sustainability held in September 2024, and updated following that meeting. It is presented as a set of slides, because it is also intended as input material to a pitch to potential long-term sponsors of it. Such sponsor pitches are now being planned, and will be undertaken in the year ahead through the support of LAREB.

This deliverable therefore summarises the work undertaken by ConcePTION WP6 in collaboration with the Sustainability Task Force to encapsulate the value of MUMS, and the results of engaging a multi stakeholder expert group in reviewing, improving this pitch, and helping to champion the wider recognition of MUMS and potential sponsorship for sustainability. WP6 worked with WP5 and the sustainability task force to establish a championing community, in particular through a multi-stakeholder workshop held in September 2024, reported in this deliverable.

It is unfortunate that the time needed to win decision-maker support and corresponding funding for MUMS is slow and was commenced relatively late in the project, once the definitive shape and ideal growth trajectory of MUMS had become clear. As a consequence, the project closed without having identified an adopting country or sponsor, but is fortunate LAREB has offered to sustain the resource for a year giving extra time to find a funded sustainability and growth solution.

Introduction

This deliverable reports on the successful efforts and results from establishing a multi-stakeholder community to help define and subsequently make ongoing contributions to a sustainability strategy for one of the main results arising from the ConcePTION project, Mothers Using Medicines Safely (MUMS).

Work package 6 of the project (WP6) has had the responsibility to help to fashion suitable external stakeholder engagement to support the work and results of the scientific work packages. In the final two years of the project the focus of WP6 shifted from work packages to results clusters. These are shown in Figure 1 below, reproduced from the project's Sustainability Task Force. Out of these, the Knowledge Bank, branded as MUMS, has been considered to be the most viable result for which a multi-stakeholder advisory and promoting community could be within the scope of WP6 to foster.

Figure 1: The three clusters of sustainable results from the IHI ConcePTION project, as depicted by its Sustainability Task Force

Figure 1 firstly divides the sustainable results of the project into knowledge generation and knowledge dissemination areas. Knowledge generation is further divided into data driven scientific studies and breastmilk specific studies, each of which has determined its own communities to engage with. WP6 has contributed to the thinking around how to motivate stakeholders to commit to activities within sustainable networks to generate new knowledge through research, and other stakeholders to fund that new knowledge generation. This has included questions about the relationship that should be fashioned and the terms that should be negotiated with data access providers and study centres, and sustainable business model considerations from a multi stakeholder perspective. This WP6 input has been detailed within other project deliverables, such as D8.2.

This deliverable focuses on Mothers using Medicines Safely (MUMS) which is an online resource summarising in lay friendly terms the evidence of safety about the use of these medicines in pregnancy. (Whilst breastfeeding is also in scope of the project, it has for the moment been considered out of scope for MUMS, for resource reasons.) This project result was considered the most important for WP6 focus on engaging diverse stakeholders, in order to help guide its growth to viability and utility, its adoption and its sustainability.

Methodology

Work package 6 of ConcePTION has the scope to guide the scientific work packages in how to most effectively engage with external stakeholders during the conduct of their research and innovation activities and, later in the project, how best to foster an appropriate multi-stakeholder community to support the sustainability of the project results. In earlier years of the project WP6 formalised methodologies for engaging with external stakeholders, considering regulatory stakeholders, clinical research stakeholders and wider health systems and public stakeholders. It developed frameworks, guidelines, methodologies and templates to help formalise these engagements, which have been published in earlier project deliverables.

Since November 2022, WP6 has worked closely with the Sustainability Task Force, established by WP8, to examine the targeted and results of the project and consider what external stakeholder engagements and community building might be most suitable to help with sustainability.

Through a series of meetings in 2022-23 with workpackages 1, 2 and 7, jointly convened by WP6 and the Sustainability Task Force, the viability of a real-world data study network (comprising both real-world data retrospective studies and prospective studies) was examined. The market facing perspective for this network was considered to be primarily the pharmaceutical sector who might fund evidence generation studies, and the medicines regulators whose engagement is important to promote the appropriate acceptability and decision-making value of real-world data evidence on medicine safety in pregnancy and breastfeeding. The relationship of these work packages with the medicines regulators is documented in another WP6 deliverable, D6.4. WP6 also highlighted the importance of establishing sound business to business relationships between any centralised entity that coordinates the design and contact of safety studies and the federated network of study centres (data access providers) who would undertake local data management and data provision, and potentially also be clinical trial centres for prospective studies. Success factors for these B2B relationships were formulated and handed over to WPs 1 and 2 to take forward. The outcome of these negotiations and the sustainability of the study network is reported in other deliverables.

A parallel set of meetings was held with WP4 regarding the sustainability of the breast milk network. It was agreed that the BBMRI is the best matched community to support efforts to sustain a European breastmilk network, with which the WP4 leadership already had very good relationships. After initial discussions, it was agreed that there was no further role for WP6 in supporting this project result.

From early 2023 WP6 therefore focused most of its attention on the results arising from WP5, which are shown in Figure 1 as the knowledge dissemination results.

It soon transpired that the e-learning platform developed by WP5 would be hosted by and promoted by the Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland (RCSI). It is likely to target continuing professional development and undergraduate training facilities across Europe, and will be responsible for defining and reaching out to these communities. It was therefore agreed that this will not be a focal point of activity for WP6.

Attention therefore focused on MUMS, starting from spring 2023. Through a series of meetings WP6 members gained a detailed understanding of what had been developed in order to verify the requirements for an online resource of information about the safe use of medicines in pregnancy, and the complementarity of this resource to the existing medicines information services provided by teratologist information services in some European countries. The meetings also clarified what had so far been designed and implemented including the extent of population of the MUMS resource with actual medicines content, and the governance procedure that had quality assured this content.

These insights were used to formulate an initial summary document, presenting the case for MUMS. These insights are summarised in the next chapter of this deliverable.

Once this case had been well formulated, some early approaches were made by WP5 to charitable foundations including the Gates Foundation and WHO, but were not successful at attracting funding. WP6 therefore agreed to support WP5 by creating a detailed and highly visual pitch presentation, and to convene a large multi-stakeholder workshop to help refine the concept, provide guidance on priority settings with regard to medicines content, initial countries to target for uptake, matters such as language translations and dissemination channels, and importantly which national and transnational bodies might consider favourably financially supporting the growth and early uptake of MUMS. After many months of preparation, this workshop was held in September 2024. It generated valuable insights in all of these areas, and also helped to establish a network of experts across Europe who have indicated willingness to continue to engage with MUMS team and to support its efforts to scale and sustain.

The case for sustaining MUMS

This chapter summarises the case for MUMS, as might be provided within an introductory briefing or grant proposal to a sponsor. A much more detailed and visual pitch is provided in Chapter 4.

Stakeholder needs

Women who are pregnant, breastfeeding, or intending to get pregnant need at times to take medication for existing or new health conditions. They inevitably want to be confident that the medicines they are taking will not put their pregnancy or baby at risk. Many women would like access to trusted information sources of information, in an understandable form, that could guide them about the evidence on medicines safety in this situation. Health professionals would normally be the point of contact to seek that advice, but they themselves sometimes struggle to find the most relevant, objective and up-to-date information to guide their patients. It is of vital importance that women who wish to look up information about medicines they are currently taking, have been prescribed or recommended to take, can easily find trustworthy information that is written in a style that is easy to understand and accessible in their first language.

Why MUMS is needed

Lay-friendly web information resources about the use of medicines in pregnancy and breastfeeding are developed by Teratology Information Services in some countries and sometimes regulatory or HTA bodies. Many countries, including in Europe, do not have such centres, or have centres that have the expertise but not the resources to develop, provide and maintain up to date medicines safety evidence for the public in their country in a comprehensive manner. In those countries, and for women in any country not able to read the national language (particularly those from underserved sub-populations such as first-generation immigrants or refugees) women often have to rely upon Internet searches. That inevitably presents them with a mixture of lack of information or of information of variable readability, quality, and reliability, leading to the risk of misinformation, misunderstanding and ultimately potential lack of required treatment. MUMS has been developed to cater for this need, and deliberately not to directly duplicate the services that already exist.

To verify this need, and to inform the design of the MUMS portal, ConcePTION partners undertook a mixed methods study comprising desk research, online surveys and interviews, the results of which are published in WP5 deliverables. These studies confirmed the need for, and the likely use by, women and HCPs in Europe of a medicines knowledge bank to guide their medicines choices during pregnancy and breastfeeding, and to empower them to have informed joint decision-making conversations with their healthcare professionals.

The participating users also stated the following requirements for MUMS.

- The information provided on the portal should be clear and understandable for both HCPs and the general public.
- The information pages should be easily found and have a clear conclusion. It is also important that the information is available in different languages.
- In order to increase reliability and trust, it should be clear on which evidence the presented information was based.
- The pharmaceutical industry should not be involved in generating or validating the content.

Across Europe, the majority of healthcare professionals also have experienced finding contradictory information about medicines use during pregnancy/breastfeeding. In countries with an available

TIS-based source, HCPs considered this source sufficient, and they used it regularly. The published analysis of discrepancies between different information sources for both health care professionals (HCPs) and patients in online information sources confirmed discrepancies in online information sources regarding safety of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding are common. Recommendations from the teratology information services (TIS) showed better consistency, indicating that on a scientific level there is more consensus. HCPs might therefore find the MUMS resource useful for their own information if they do not have access to a resource provided by a TIS, perhaps because it is more up-to-date than the other resources they have access to, or more easy to understand in a short clinical consultation time frame. They might also choose to recommend the resource to their pregnant patients, to back up the advice they have themselves given regarding the use of a particular medicine.

The conclusion from these public and professional stakeholder surveys was that MUMS should provide free, trustworthy, accurate, up to date and easy to understand medicines information in order to:

- help to avoid the use of unsafe medicines that might risk the development and health of the baby, or might harm the pregnancy;
- encourage appropriate medicines use and adherence to treatment, so that concurrent illnesses are optimally managed, also reducing the risk from the disease to the development and health of the baby and of harm during the pregnancy;
- enable better informed shared decision-making between the woman and her healthcare professionals
- reduce health systems utilisation and cost by avoiding interventions to treat preventable complications through inappropriate medicines use or poor adherence;
- contribute to the pooling of evidence about the safe use of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding, assisting with future regulatory and health professional decision making.

Due to the collaboration of several TIS centres, all part of ENTIS, it will be possible to ensure that the guidance published in MUMS has been agreed upon by international experts, so that women across Europe are given consistent information and advice.

Content development

MUMS presents simple, easy to understand summaries of the latest scientific evidence regarding the safety of medicines during pregnancy, as single pages per medicine, which can be found through searching by drug name, drug category or disease. It also includes pages about diseases, summarising the treatment options for that disease. This allows women to understand the safety evidence for different drugs used to treat a condition, which they might be taking or recommended/prescribed.

MUMS can be accessed from the following website: <https://www.mums.eu>

The information in the MUMS knowledge bank has been written by members of the European Network of Teratology Information Services, ENTIS. This group of experts evaluates evidence and disseminates summarised information to contribute to the primary prevention of birth defects and developmental disorders.

The MUMS team within the project identified the priority medicines to include, then the most up-to-date sources from across the TIS centres and other publicly available sources. The editorial process included validating how current and complete the source pages are and re-expressing and usually further summarising the information to be suitable for a reader with lower reading literacy. This is undertaken by experts from national TIS centres in the ConcePTION consortium, who produce a standardised lay summary according to the MUMS template and authoring guidelines, in English, which is cross-checked by other experts before being incorporated into the portal. A further quality

assured process has been defined for language translations, and translation has started for Italian and Polish.

Deployment strategy

MUMS targets countries and languages for which today there is little or no trusted information source on medicines use in pregnancy and breastfeeding, and for which searching the web is the current practice. This includes expatriate and Immigrant communities which may not feel comfortable with the language of their local information source. MUMS does not expect to be accessed, used or promoted in countries that already have access to trusted information from a national TIS centre, although it might be accessed by people in those countries if they would like information in another language or in a lower reading literacy form than local resources

The case for a sponsorship funding model

Funding is required to widen the medicines content coverage, translate the lay summaries into multiple languages, to ensure the existing content remains up-to-date and clinically accurate, and for promotion. Several national Teratology Information Service centres have agreed to make their medicines information content available to MUMS to repackage and reuse, at no cost, so the required funding is to assimilate, streamline and quality check this content, and to translate, host and promote the portal.

It is intended that the MUMS knowledge bank is freely available. It is therefore unlikely that a licensing or membership model will be practical to develop and administer. Industry sponsorship is deliberately not being considered, and would not be acceptable, since MUMS must demonstrably be free from any concerns about a conflict of interest with the marketing authorisation holders of medicinal products. A sponsorship model is therefore being pursued, through charitable agencies and/or public funding, so that the resource can always be open access to the public and health professionals. For individual country translations, deployment, promotion of uptake and support the potential for financial backing from a health ministry will also be pursued.

Next steps following the multi-stakeholder workshop

The multi stakeholder workshop was held in Brussels on 23rd and 24 September 2024. Significant effort was expended on preparing a comprehensive but visual presentation of the initiative, its rationale, its functions, options for its extension and options for its funding. The material, presented as slides in Chapter 4, was updated following the workshop and serves now also as a workshop report.

Follow-up discussions are taking place with stakeholders from the Czech Republic, whom are developing also a knowledge bank, and the potential for future collaboration into 2025 is being explored. Follow-up discussions are also taking place with stakeholders from Poland. Work is in progress on the translation of MUMS and on a roadmap for implementation in Poland (which may be an example for other countries). This collaboration will be continued in 2025 via Lareb. In addition, follow-up discussions with contacts in Romania are ongoing.

The stakeholders who participated in the September event have been invited to become part of MUMS community, along with future collaborators who are interested to contribute after the ConcePTION project ends in December 2024.

Discussion

The WP5 experts from teratology information services, working with other public and industry partners, identified early on the need for reliable and easily understood information about the safety of medicines that might be appropriate to use during pregnancy and lactation. This is primarily needed in countries that do not have an existing information resource, including many in Europe. Although targeting women, it is clear that health professionals often lack the same information and would find it useful.

The WP MUMS design team invested a lot of time in defining the structure and layout of this resource, developing an editorial policy and governance for content creation, and then a web based implementation. As the work progressed it became more clear that developing original new medicines content might prove too expensive and resource intensive, requiring expertise from a limited pool, and that re-factoring information from existing services might be more efficient as a way of growing an initial strong body of content.

Unfortunately, work to grow communities of interest in those countries which presently miss the resource and connections with possible decision makers and other funders of this kind of resource was started late in the project. Since political decision-making and the allocation of public funds takes time, the result is that the project ended before any sustainable commitments could be made by any one country. Fortunately LAREB has agreed to sustain the resource for one year (the year 2025) after the project, giving it extra time to find willing funders within certain countries. A parallel effort is being undertaken to seek sponsorship from charitable organisations and transnational bodies like the WHO. This inevitably also raises the possibility that such sponsors might prioritise countries outside Europe.

At the time of writing, a post project WP5 team is continuing to explore these opportunities, in particular the following channels:

- WHO: After presenting recently at WHO-UMC, the MUMS team is exploring if WHO may be interested to contribute to MUMS to enable growth of content (number of medicines) & translation for 2025.
- IHI call 9, collaborators within the ConcePTION managing team are looking into possibilities there, they would like to include MUMS and eLearning (this call opens early 2025)
- ENTIS may be interested to contribute to the hosting costs.

As a possible sponsors include the Bosch Foundation, the Melinda Gates foundation and Women's Inc.

Conclusion

During its last two years, work package 6, through Task 6.5, has worked closely with the sustainability task force and with multiple scientific work packages to understand their strategies towards and growing their efforts and results post project, and what kinds of community building might be relevant to support them. Having engaged across all of them, work package 6 focused attention on MUMS because it seemed to have the strongest viability and a reliance upon growing a community of championing stakeholders. WP6 worked with WP5 and the sustainability task force to establish such a championing community, in particular through a multi-stakeholder workshop held in September 2024, reported in this deliverable. It is unfortunate that the time needed to win decision-maker support and corresponding funding for MUMS is slow and was commenced relatively late in

the project, once the definitive shape and ideal growth trajectory of MUMS had become clear. As a consequence, the project closed without having identified an adopting country or sponsor, but is fortunate LAREB has offered to sustain the resource for a year giving extra time to find a funded sustainability and growth solution.

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Detailed presentation of MUMS and outcomes from the multi-stakeholder meeting

concePTION
SAFETY EVIDENCE ECOSYSTEM

ConcePTION Workshop 2024
23–24 September, Brussels, Belgium
Meeting Report

The research leading to these results has received support from the EU/EFPIA Innovative Medicines Initiative [2] Joint Undertaking
ConcePTION grant n° 821520

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ConcePTION and MUMS

<h3>ConcePTION project</h3> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ConcePTION project, launched in April 2019, is part of the Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI), co-funded by the European Union and EFPIA (European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations). • Aims to build an ecosystem that generates and disseminates reliable, consistent information about the use and safety of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding. • Brings together more than 80 organizations, including regulatory agencies, academia, and industry partners. 	<h3>MUMS Knowledge Bank (KB)</h3> <p>MUMS (Medicines Use in Mothers Safety) is a publicly accessible, free knowledge bank under the ConcePTION initiative.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aims to become the primary, trusted pan-European source of reliable information on the safety of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding. • Designed to provide clear, consistent, and validated information in multiple languages, removing ambiguities surrounding medication use for pregnant and breastfeeding women. • Currently holds information on around 40 medicines, with plans to expand to over 200 medicines in the near future.
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The research leading to these results has received support from the EU/EFPIA Innovative Medicines Initiative [2] Joint Undertaking
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ConcePTION Workshop 2024

The ConcePTION Workshop 2024 was organized to gain insights from various stakeholders to tackle the issue of sustainability of the MUMS KB. The event kicked off with a welcome dinner on the evening of September 23rd, allowing attendees to connect informally in a relaxed setting. After dinner, the MUMS KB was demonstrated, followed by a discussion.

The main workshop on September 24th included:

- An introduction to the conception project and the MUMS KB.
- A presentation of three pre-worked scenarios for the way forward.
- Moderated, structured discussions and voting on the key topics.

The overall focus was to support the project's sustainability beyond the current timeline, drawing on the diverse expertise and experiences of the attendees.

This report summarises key insights from the meeting.

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Goals of the Workshop

How do we make MUMS sustainable?

- Review and discuss **three potential scenarios**
- Identify **minimal requirements** and discuss growth development
- Discuss how to make the **information broadly available** and taken-up
- Define how to **achieve funding**

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 conception

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Methodology: voting and discussions

- A diverse range of stakeholders from multiple countries were present at the meeting.
- The programme included a **demo of the MUMS KB prototype**, an introduction to the challenges facing MUMS, and focused discussions on the key focus themes.
- Voting was conducted on various aspects of the workshop discussions to ensure that the conclusions and recommendations reflected a consensus-driven approach.
- **Videos featuring women** sharing their personal experiences of accessing knowledge on drug safety during pregnancy were presented to highlight the real-world impact and importance of MUMS KB and set the context for the discussions.

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 conception

Moderators and presenters

Moderators/Presenters	Position and Organization
Ingrid Klingmann	Chairman, European Forum for Good Clinical Practice (EFGCP)
Dipak Kalra	President, European Institute for Innovation through Health Data (i-HD)
Marjolein Willemen	Medical Policy & External Collaborations Lead, Novartis
Stéphanie Tcherny-Lessenot	Head of Benefit-Risk Evaluation, Patient Safety & Pharmacovigilance, Sanofi
Miranda van Tuyl	Head of Teratology Information Service & Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register (Moeders van Morgen Lareb)
Paul Roberts	Co-founder & Director, Dialogue
Andrea Levy	Co-founder & Director, Dialogue
Pieter Stolk	Head of Project Management Office, ConcePTION

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Meeting attendees

Name	Organization	Name	Organization
Aleksandra Wesolowska	Warszawski Uniwersytet Medyczny - WUM	Laura De Meester	AFMPS - FAGG
Amanda Neville	University of Ferrara	Laure Sillis	KU Leuven
Ano Maita	Mothers for Mothers Association	Lieve Franssen	Telenet
Anca Burnei	Romanian Society for Obstetrics and Gynaecology	Livia Nagy Bonnard	ESCNH
Ann van den Broucke	AFMPS - FAGG	Mandy Daly	Irish Neonatal Health Alliance
Barbora Košťálová	Charles University, Hradec Králové	Martin Jens Persson	HKR
Benedikte Cuppers	Lareb	Mary Lynne Van Poelgeest-Pomfret	EFGCP
Bryan Michaux	EFGCP	Michael Ceulemans	KU Leuven
Cristina Rotaru	Victor Babes Uni. of Medicine and Pharmacy, Timisoara	Nicola Bedlington	Millwater Partners/The Synergist
Eline Tommelein	VUB Belgium	Patrik Vankrunkelsven	KU Leuven
France Donnay	The Synergist	Puccini Aurora	Emilia Romagna Regional Health Authority
Georgios Eleftheriou	Barts Health NHS Trust	Roshini Beenukumar	Sapiens Medical Writing
Ida Niklson	IDDA Pharma Consulting	Sarah Thooft	BCFI
Ioana Tobarcea	National Society of Fetal Medicine and Neonatology	Tanguy Vanderborcht	EFGCP
Jana Popova	EUPATI	Tatyana Benisheva	Medical University Sofia
		Viviane Klingmann	University of Düsseldorf

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ConcePTION: mission and objectives

Marjolein Willemen introduced the mission of the IMI ConcePTION project, key statistics on the current status of medicines use during pregnancy and key focus areas of the project.

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IMI ConcePTION: A force for change

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- Launched in April 2019 to build an ecosystem that can generate quicker and better evidence on the safety of medicines during pregnancy and lactation, and to ensure that this information reaches pregnant and breastfeeding women and their healthcare professionals (HCPs), enabling them to make evidence-based decisions.
- The consortium consists of over 80 public and private sector organisations from academia, regulatory agencies, and industry and is funded by the EC's Innovative Medicines Initiative (IMI).

The mission is to empower and enable pregnant and breastfeeding women to make important decisions about medicines use during pregnancy and breastfeeding.

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The MUMS Knowledge Bank

Stéphanie Tcherny-Lessenot introduced the current gaps in information on medicines use during pregnancy and breastfeeding, the MUMS website prototype, and the need to expand, maintain, and raise awareness about its existence.

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Current gaps in access to reliable and consistent information on medicine when pregnant or breastfeeding

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The good news

- Teratology Information Services (known as TIS) already exist in several European countries with their activities coordinated by ENTIS.
- Feedback is positive and usage levels high, suggesting that the concept works.

However,

- Many countries in Europe do not have a TIS.
- Language is often a barrier to accessing content that is available elsewhere.
- Awareness of a local TIS can be low, even in countries that do have one.

- Both TIS & Knowledge bank
- Only Knowledge bank
- Only TIS
- No TIS or Knowledge bank

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MUMS aims to bridge the current information gap

What is MUMS?

- A free-to-use, publicly accessible bank of reliable information about the use of medicines during pregnancy and when breastfeeding.

With the goal of becoming...

- The pan-European source of trusted information on the safety of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding, available in all required languages.

- Initial prototype contains 40 drugs in English
- Goal is to reach 200 (and beyond)
- Translations available in Italian and Polish

Five key benefits of MUMS

Easy to use

Users can search using drug name, drug category and disease, ensuring information can be accessed quickly and easily.

Clear

Explanations use simple language and have a clear conclusion, allowing users to move forward with confidence.

Consistent

Content is agreed by Teratology Information Service experts from countries that are part of ENTIS, removing ambiguity and inconsistency.

Independent

We've not sought pharma industry sponsorship for MUMS, eliminating the risk of conflict of interest.

Tested

We've consulted and tested the product with user groups, to ensure we deliver the best possible user experience.

The MUMS website demo

Miranda van Tuyl showcased the functionalities of the current MUMS website prototype, followed by a discussion with the workshop participants.

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 conception

The MUMS website: demo

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The website provides reliable information on the safety of medicines during pregnancy, gathered from existing knowledge banks across Europe.

- The pages dedicated to a drug have a lay summary for pregnant/breastfeeding women and more detailed information for healthcare providers.
- The content is being translated into multiple European languages. However, if an existing reliable knowledge bank is available in a specific language (e.g., the Dutch Lareb), the user is redirected to it.
- The website has not been actively promoted to end users.

Highlights from the demo:

Search functionality: The website currently allows searching by compound names only.

Quality-assured content development and updates: The information on the website is reviewed and updated by a panel of experts to ensure accuracy and relevance. The goal is to keep the website dynamic and frequently updated to maintain its credibility and usefulness.

E-learning modules for HCPs: The website includes information on E-learning for HCPs, which is currently being tested at a university in Ireland with plans to expand to other universities and healthcare professionals across Europe.

Maternal medical conditions section: Provides indication-specific pregnancy-related information.

Funding and sustainability: Ensuring the long-term sustainability of the website is dependent on securing adequate funding.

 innovative medicines initiative

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 conception

The MUMS website: SWOT analysis based on discussions*

*Scenario-specific SWOT analysis is included in the later part of the report

Strengths:

- Content reviewed by teratology experts who are part of ENTIS
- Available in English and two other European languages (Italian and Polish)
- Available free-of-charge to both lay and expert audiences

Weaknesses:

- Search by country-specific brand names is not currently possible
- Currently limited to 38 drugs and 5 medical conditions in two languages other than English
- Minimal user engagement and awareness of the website among the target audience of young, pregnant women

Opportunities:

- Potential to collaborate with popular pregnancy websites and apps to increase awareness and referrals
- Seeking endorsements from reputable organizations like ENTIS to enhance credibility and trustworthiness
- Developing a social media strategy, including influencer engagement, to reach young, pregnant women effectively
- A trustworthy, scientific, and neutral source of information.

Threats:

- Competition from other less reliable and trustworthy online sources of information
- Difficulty in keeping the website updated and relevant, especially without secure funding.
- Potential legal and regulatory challenges in providing safety information on medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding.
- The transient nature of pregnancy and breastfeeding makes maintaining awareness difficult.

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Sustainability of MUMS

To ensure the service can continue to be free-to-use from 2025 onwards, funding is required to:

- Ensure ongoing maintenance of all content so it remains up to date.
- Increase the number of drugs included from 40 to 200, the number we regard as the viable minimum.
- Translate content into prioritised languages.

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The three suggested routes forward

Miranda van Tuyl presented three potential scenarios for the expansion of MUMS beyond the current prototype.

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The three scenarios at-a-glance

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- To focus on the most frequently used medicines in pregnancy and provide that information in English
- To focus on the most frequently used medicines in pregnancy, but per country in local languages including country-specific brand names
- To focus on the most frequently used and newly marketed medicines for selected disease areas only.

Single source | Degree of localisation | Localised

Selected (40) | Coverage of medicines | All (X,000)

Now | Current prototype | Most used in pregnancy | Indication specific | Future

“Country-specific” | “Most frequent” | “Therapy area focused”

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Scenario 1: Most frequent

Most frequent

- Increase content in EN to 200+ medicines focusing on those most used in pregnancy (MVP).
- Use substance name.
- Include OTC medicines.
- Include information on breastfeeding.
- Keep fully up-to-date.
- Communicate availability across Europe and extend globally?

Pros:

- Accurate and relevant medicine descriptions
- Leverage existing TIS centre expertise
- Scalability to expand beyond 200 medicines
- Includes medicines suitable for breastfeeding mothers
- Not limited to the EU

Gaps/risks:

- Limited to English language
- Potential overlap with existing resources in English or national languages

Strategy:

- Two-year project to grow to 200+ medicines in English
- Ensuring information is up-to-date
- General launch in Europe

Scenario 2: Country-specific

Country-specific

- Provide information on 200 most frequently used medicines in that country including OTC.
- Aided by AI, translate into priority languages with local partner validation.
- Use national brand names.
- Collaborate with local TIS.
- Communicate availability to relevant countries only.

Pros:

- Information available in selected local languages across Europe.
- Ensures we have a teratology information contact point in countries lacking such a service.

Gaps/risks:

- Less content available initially.
- Need for teratology experts fluent in translated languages.
- Liability for translated content.

Strategy:

- Prioritize local collaboration.
- Translate current content into four European languages.
- Include local brand names.
- Expand database to 200+ medicines (including translations).
- Ensure all information remains up-to-date.

Scenario 3: Therapy area focused

Therapy area focused

- Provide information in EN on most frequently used and newly marketed medicines for selected disease areas only.
- Use substance name.
- Include OTC medicines.
- Collaborate with specialised HCP/patient groups
- Communicate availability across Europe through audience-relevant channels.

Pros:

- Centralised access to all information for specific medical conditions
- Developed in collaboration with healthcare professionals and patient organisations

Gaps/risks:

- Limited information on commonly used medicines.
- Relevance only for a specific patient group.
- Potential for fewer return visits once treatment is established.
- Current expert group may not support the original MUMS concept.

Strategy:

- Two-year project to include all relevant medicines for the target disease area
- Rollout through healthcare professionals and patient organisations
- Ensure information remains up-to-date

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Stakeholder discussions: Which scenario do you prefer?

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Scenario 2, the country-specific approach was the preferred choice

- Most participants preferred the country-specific approach as it addresses the areas of greatest need as well as language barriers. The "frequently used medicines" scenario (scenario 1) was the second favourite, but participants raised concerns about its limited language coverage.
- The "therapy area" scenario (scenario 3) was the least preferred option, but some speakers highlighted the advantages of the approach. Combining two scenarios or adopting a one-after-the-other approach was also discussed.

Scenario 2, the country-specific approach was the preferred choice

"The country-specific option I like, because you can play to the countries that have the most need."

"There is much more need for information in other languages".

"I think the focus should be towards countries which don't have any service available."

"I think now, personally, if a woman asked me where to find information, and most women nowadays speak English at least a bit. I would not recommend MUMS. I would recommend BUMPS (from the UK) for medicine. I would recommend MotherToBaby (from USA) for symptoms, because it is much broader....it must be in Czech language, local language, or with the Czech brand names, as we discussed, because then it has an added value to the English existing knowledge bank, which is already on Google, available free of access."

"I also like the idea of combining scenario one and two, because they think it's a great way to also overcome the language barrier."

"I think the therapy area focused has an advantage of giving you a kickstart, and also it covers a really important need that women, for instance, with epilepsy, need to know before they even plan being pregnant."

SWOT analysis of scenario 1: Most frequent

Strengths:

- A manageable starting point by focussing on the 200 most frequently used medicines.
- Likely to be relevant and in high demand for the majority of the target audience.
- Estimated to have a reasonable cost of around 250K per year to produce and maintain the content.
- Can leverage existing trusted sources to gather this information efficiently.

Weaknesses:

- Does not address the need for information in national languages across Europe.
- Does not address the full spectrum of needs such as information on newly marketed drugs.
- Difficulty in identifying most relevant frequently used medicines.
- Precludes the option to use local brand names as the site contains generic content.

Opportunities:

- A strong foundation to expand the content over time.
- Potential to leverage AI-powered translation tools to quickly make the English content available in multiple languages.
- Possibility of collaborating with national organizations and regulatory bodies to promote the resource and integrate it with existing platforms.
- Opportunity to establish MUMS as a trusted source of information for the most commonly used medicines.

Threats:

- Risk of not adequately addressing the language needs of the target audiences in various European countries.
- Potential lack of buy-in or engagement from national-level stakeholders if the approach is perceived as too centralized.
- Competition from other less reliable and less trustworthy online sources of information

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SWOT analysis of scenario 2: Country specific

Strengths:

- Ability to tailor the content to the specific needs and language requirements of each target country.
- Potential to better address the needs of underserved and underprivileged populations in different countries.
- Allows for better integration with existing national healthcare systems and information sources.
- Ability to cater to language and cultural nuances in multilingual countries.
- Provide product- and country-specific information, including information from national patient leaflets.

Weaknesses:

- More resource-intensive in terms of funding and coordination efforts to develop and maintain multiple country-specific versions.
- Challenges in keeping up with the constantly changing landscape of marketed products in each country.
- Potential lack of consistency or standardization across the different country-specific versions.

Opportunities:

- Ability to partner with national-level stakeholders, such as healthcare providers, pharmacies, and patient organizations, to promote and integrate the resource.
- Potential to leverage existing national-level websites and platforms to host and distribute the country-specific content.
- Opportunity to address the specific language and cultural needs of each target audience, improving accessibility, trust and engagement.
- Opportunity to create a central framework that local partners can implement in their respective countries.

Threats:

- Challenges in developing a harmonized approach due to differences in regulations, healthcare systems, and cultural attitudes across countries.
- Difficulty securing funding and resources for multiple country-specific versions.
- Misinformation and anti-science movements may require additional strategies to build trust.
- Possible resistance from national-level stakeholders to collaborate.

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SWOT analysis of scenario 3: TA focus

Strengths:

- Ability to focus on therapeutic areas that have the greatest need and impact, such as women with epilepsy.
- Potential to provide more comprehensive and tailored information for women with chronic conditions who need to make informed decisions about medication during pregnancy.
- Opportunity to establish the MUMS resource as a trusted and authoritative source of information in these key therapeutic areas, building strong credibility and trust.

Weaknesses:

- Limited scope, which may restrict overall reach and effectiveness.
- Challenges in pinpointing shared therapeutic areas that are significant and prioritized across various countries.
- For patented medications, inconsistencies may arise between the different patient leaflets.

Opportunities:

- Ability to collaborate with patient organizations, healthcare providers, and regulatory bodies focused on the target therapeutic areas with the potential for deeper engagement and advocacy from these stakeholders.
- Opportunity to position MUMS as a comprehensive and authoritative source of information for women with chronic conditions who are planning or experiencing pregnancy.

Threats:

- Difficulty in securing funding and resources for a more specialized approach, especially if it is perceived as less inclusive or comprehensive.
- Potential resistance from national-level stakeholders if the therapy-area-specific approach is not aligned with their priorities.
- Possible public perception issues if the platform is perceived as favouring certain pharmaceutical companies or therapeutic areas, undermining its credibility as a neutral resource.

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Stakeholder discussions:
Minimum requirements for each route

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Target audiences

Primary target audiences

- The group agreed to **focus on pregnant women rather than pregnant and breastfeeding women** as the primary target audience as a starting point, not because they regarded support for breastfeeding medicines as unimportant, but to be pragmatic and focus the use of resources.
- **HCPs, including physicians, midwives, and pharmacists** were recognized as another key target audience for the information, with the group agreeing that both the user and prescriber audiences are equally important and should be targeted with the same product.

VOTING: Should the initial target audience be limited to pregnancy, or should it include both pregnancy...

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Primary target audiences

“If I were to promote this, I would firstly go to them and promote the platform at the point of purchase (referring to pharmacies).”

We've got two sides here, haven't we? We've got the women and the healthcare professionals who they're going to be talking to, who's going to be their conversation partner”

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 CONCEPTION

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Secondary/specialized target audiences

- **Patient associations:** It was suggested to include patient associations, as they can provide valuable input and represent the perspective of women with certain diseases.
- **Non-medically trained educators:** It was suggested to include non-medically trained educators, such as prenatal educators, as they are often accessed by pregnant women, particularly in rural areas, for information and support.
- **Women of reproductive age:** The website should also aim to provide information to women of reproductive age, even before they become pregnant, to help with family planning and medication decisions.
- **Pregnant women/women planning pregnancy with chronic conditions:** Reaching women with chronic conditions like epilepsy who need to make informed decisions about medication during pregnancy, or even planning for pregnancy, need to be considered
- **Pregnant women belonging to underserved/underprivileged populations:** Reaching women in rural or disadvantaged areas, such as parts of Romania, was highlighted as an important consideration.

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 CONCEPTION

Secondary/specialized target audiences

“We call them prenatal educators....and they are not medically trained, but they are accessed by women quite frequently for childhood preparation classes, for breastfeeding health.”

“I know we didn't say we were going ahead with therapy- specific, but I do think we ought to involve patient associations.”

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Number and type of products to make available

Medicines most used in pregnancy?

How many products to start with?

Newly marketed products?

Other considerations?

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Number and type of products to make available

All participant agreed that 200 most commonly searched-for products, which would likely be mostly generics and over-the-counter (OTC) drugs, is a reasonable number for a national launch.

- There was a debate about whether to focus on the 200 most commonly prescribed medicines or the 200 greatest knowledge gaps. Participants ultimately agreed that the 200 most commonly searched-for products were a suitable approach.
- The group also discussed including **supplements, homeopathic medicines, and other non-conventional products** as a second layer of information, recognizing their importance to patients despite their non-conventional nature.
- The need to provide clear information for **newly marketed products** was emphasized, primarily because there is often unfamiliarity with these products, even if the information exists.

VOTING: Is the 200 most commonly searched-for drugs a reasonable number for a national launch?

Number and type of products to make available

Sources of information and collaboration

Existing information providers

Current procedure: MUMS currently collaborates with existing trusted information sources, such as the British, Swedish, Dutch, German and American Teratology Knowledge Banks, and uses the information available as the primary source. The MUMS content team reviews the content in these knowledge bases, which was described as consistent and reliable, and then uses that as the basis for creating summaries. References and links back to the original trusted source websites are included. Any new literature or information that may not be on the source websites are also included along with the links as reference.

Sources of information and collaboration

Improving the trustworthiness of MUMS:

- Many participants mentioned that **getting endorsement and approval from national and regional health authorities and having their symbol on the MUMS webpage** would be crucial for the information to be seen as trustworthy by HCPs and patients.
- **Collaborating with national professional societies**, such as Gynaecology Associations, was also identified as an important factor for building credibility and trust.
- **Endorsements from EU-level institutions** and collaboration between different European countries were discussed as beneficial to building trust and credibility.
- It was also noted that involving patient organizations could help increase trust among the target audience—pregnant women and new mothers.

VOTING: Is a pan-European collaboration trustworthy enough to get acceptance?

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Sources of information and collaboration

“The symbol of the Italian Gynaecologists Association, the symbol appears in what we do, and this gives us a great deal of credibility and trust.”

“...cooperation with the National Patient Organizations...will have much more weight than if it's only coming from the National Professional Societies.”

“In Romania, where the anti-science movement is on the rise...getting the national professional societies on board from the get-go is very important.”

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Language and translation requirements

Current procedure: The MUMS website is being translated into Italian and Polish. MUMS currently uses a specialized AI software for translation. The translated content is then validated by a national-level expert. The quality of the translated and expert-validated content is considered fit for purpose.

Which and how many languages?

Use of automated tool?

Validation and liability of translated content?

Other considerations?

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Language and translation requirements

- Automated translation and validation:** Most participants considered this approach, where automated AI-based tools are used for translation and getting the content verified by an expert, as a viable option. Validation by an expert was discussed as a better option than retranslation. The responsibility and, therefore, the liability of all content, including translated content, would come under MUMS.
- Cultural nuances and multilingual countries:** In multilingual countries like Belgium and countries with common languages, experts who understand both the language and cultural nuances might be needed.
- Accessibility and lay language:** The importance of using lay, simplified language (e.g., Level B1) that is easily understandable by the general public was highlighted. The group mentioned exploring the use of AI tools to help with this process of making the information more accessible.

VOTING: Is automatic translation and validation by an expert enough to get acceptance?

Language and translation requirements

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Technical requirements

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Technical requirements

- **Mobile-friendly web design:** The group agreed that the MUMS platform should have a mobile-friendly web design to ensure accessibility. A participant from Romania noted that even in rural areas, access to a smartphone and internet connection is widespread.
- **Need for an App:** Some participants expressed a preference for a mobile-friendly website over an app and others viewed having an app as helpful.
- **Automatic language detection:** The functionality to automatically detect the user's region/language and display the content in that language was seen as a positive feature.
- **Multi-accessibility features:** The potential use of AI-enabled accessibility features, such as the ability to upload a photo of a drug label and get the necessary information relayed back as a voice message, particularly in the context of reaching underserved and underprivileged populations, was discussed.
- **Indexing to improve user-friendliness:** One participant mentioned making the MUMS website more user-friendly by making it searchable by indication as well.

VOTING: Are all the technical features mentioned here necessary for acceptance?

Yes		21
No		0

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Technical requirements

"I don't install apps anymore. If your website is mobile friendly, that's enough for me, personally."

"I need an app on my smartphone....to have the answer in two or three minutes...parents coming to the intensive care unit asks, the Gynaecologist told me to use this (medication) and, because I'm breastfeeding, may I use it? So, I take out my smartphone and have the answer in two minutes."

"There are AI tools that do this, for them to take a picture of the of the packaging and then to have a voice message broadcasted back to them, whether it's safe or they should talk to GP about taking that specific drug or medication."

"I'm pregnant and I've got a really bad headache, so I look headache therapy. Or I've got epilepsy. I'm looking for information about epilepsy in pregnancy. So, we have to make sure that women and their partners are able to get that information."

Content update and expansion mechanisms

Update of product knowledge pages

Creation of new pages

Regularly?

At what frequency?

When important information is released?

How many?

Content update and expansion mechanisms

- **Regular updates:** Participants agreed on the need to keep the Knowledge Bank up-to-date (potentially annual or biannual) and expand the content and information on the platform over time as new needs and priorities emerge. In addition to the regular updates, the need for an immediate review in case of new information or triggers that warrant an update was also discussed.
- **Transparency on review and update:** The group also emphasized the need to have a clear review date visible to the public so users can easily see how current the information is. A suggestion was also made to publish a history of updates so users can easily see what has changed over time.

VOTING: Are regular updates with immediate reviews in specific situations sufficient to gain acceptance?

Content update and expansion mechanisms

“You have to have a review date.....if I read it and say, Oh, this is five years old. I don't know whether there's any new information.”

“We have an inventory of triggers, things that might initiate an immediate review.... an update to the product information, news stories, maybe from a customer, a user, who says, Hey, I was looking for this. I didn't find something. There'd be a list of triggers, and say, any of them invokes an immediate review.”

Stakeholder discussions 2: Engaging with our audiences

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What are we trying to achieve?

Our goal is for MUMS to become the most trusted and used pan-European source of information on the safety of medicines during pregnancy and breastfeeding.

To achieve that, we need to take users, prescribers and advisers on an engagement journey.

- I advocate**
I encourage others to use MUMS.
Metric = Net Promoter Score or similar
- I depend**
MUMS is my go-to resource.
Metric = visited the site on multiple occasions
- I use**
I have consulted MUMS to get advice I need.
Metric = visited the site at least once
- I'm aware**
I know what MUMS is and how to find it.
Metric = aware / unaware of the site through research

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Considerations when building awareness

Communicating to two distinct audiences

- Reaching and engaging both the user audience (pregnant/breastfeeding women) and the prescriber audience (healthcare professionals) was seen as a challenge, requiring tailored communication strategies.
- Consider the different age demographics of the user audience (younger pregnant/breastfeeding women) and the prescriber audience (older healthcare professionals).
- Informing HCP audiences was considered easier to achieve than engaging the wider target user audience of pregnant and breastfeeding women.
- The group discussed whether to have separate "healthcare professional" and "lay user" modes or to have a single-page format with a brief summary for the general public and detailed information accessible to everyone. The voting results show that the latter, a single-page format, is preferred.

VOTING: Should there be separate modes or a combined mode for the two primary audiences?

Communicating to two distinct audiences

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Social media as a primary channel

- **Reaching the younger user audience:** The group recognized that the primary user audience, pregnant and breastfeeding women, are increasingly from the Gen Z demographic (born 1996 or later). They acknowledged that this younger audience is more likely to be active on social media platforms, making a strong social media presence crucial for effectively reaching and engaging them.
- **Countering fake news and ensuring visibility:** A robust social media presence was also seen as vital to countering the proliferation of fake news and misinformation surrounding pregnancy and medication use. When users search for information online, they are likely to encounter a significant amount of unreliable or misleading content. A strong social media presence for the MUMs platform can help ensure that accurate, trustworthy information is more readily available and visible to users.
- **Specialized expertise and cost considerations:** The group acknowledged the need to potentially bring in specialized social media expertise, such as younger professionals who are more familiar with the latest trends and best practices for engaging with Gen Z and other younger user segments. As an approach would require extensive resources.

VOTING: Is social media a mandatory channel for communication?

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Social media as a primary channel

“I think it's infinitely harder to inform mothers, of course, and from a technical point of view, having a robust social media presence helps very much with countering the fake news sites.”

“If you have an influencer, And I think the costs for that can increase so largely.”

Other channels of communication

- **National HCP organizations:** Collaborating with national organizations of physicians and pharmacists and announcing the launch of the MUMS platform through their official newsletters, websites, and other channels was considered an effective way to reach HCP audiences in specific countries.
- **HCP events and conferences:** Attending and exhibiting at healthcare provider events and conferences was identified as a way to directly engage with the prescriber audience and raise awareness about the MUMS platform.

Other channels of communication

National- over European-level campaigns

- The discussion emphasized the need to balance **national-level adaptations with European-level guidance** for the success of the MUMS platform's communication and marketing efforts across countries.
- **National-level campaigns:** Most participants preferred national-level campaigns over a centralized European-level campaign, emphasizing the need to understand and adapt to country-specific cultural differences, levels of digitalization, and healthcare systems. They suggested that campaigns led at the national level, potentially through a consortium of patient and healthcare professional organizations, would be more effective. National-level endorsement and funding were seen as crucial for the campaigns' success.
- **European-level coordination and support:** The importance of incorporating a European-level perspective into campaigns was acknowledged. This involves having a centralized framework and resources at the European level, while the actual implementation and campaigning take place at the national level. This approach can promote consistency and collaboration across national efforts, while still allowing country-specific adaptations.
- **Challenges:** There were concerns about whether all countries would be willing to provide the necessary funding and resources to support national-level campaigns. Additionally, there was a concern about potentially leaving behind a majority of European countries if the initial focus was on only a select few.

National- over European-level campaigns

"I would much rather have a national campaign than a European level campaign because different cultural differences are still very steep,two former communist countries like Romania and Latvia, very different perspectives on communication, very different levels of digitalisation."

"I like the concept of it being championed from within the country. I think that the European level needs to look after the overall quality management of each national endeavour, but the more level ownership, the better."

Discussion 3: Achieving funding to sustain MUMS

Funding requirements and challenges

The key challenge is finding a model that can provide initial funding to keep the project going, while also developing a longer-term self-sustaining approach that doesn't rely too heavily on a single source. Achieving this balance within a one-year timeframe was identified as a critical priority.

- The IMI Conception project that has been supporting the work will end on December 31st this year, so there is an urgent need to find new funding to continue the project.
- LAREB will continue hosting and supporting the MUMS website for a further 12 months.
- The funding solutions must be achievable within a one-year timeframe, considering that some funding organizations can take a long time to make decisions and release funds.
- The group also identified the need to find a long-term self-sustaining model for the project rather than relying on short-term grants.

Funding requirements and challenges

"I think we have to find solutions that are achievable in one year, and that is already a limiting factor, because some of the funding organizations take quite long before they come to any decision before they agree, before the contracts are made and before the money is then really flowing."

"I think the critical aspect would be to make the decision which funders to approach, really now, between now and end of the project, at least, and have the first contact there to get this whole process going."

Sources of funding

To ensure the continued success and growth of the MUMS project, a multi-pronged approach, combining short-term funding solutions with the development of a long-term self-sustaining model, would be necessary. The group explored the following funding sources.

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European-level funding opportunities

European research funding: Although there is a potential for pursuing research-based funding for the project, there were some concerns raised. The project may currently be beyond the stage of a typical research project and more focused on implementation. Pursuing research-focused EU funding would bring the burden of a research portfolio, which may not be the most appropriate approach for the current needs of the project. In addition, such funding opportunities can only be explored as a medium-term solution as they typically can take up to a year or more to obtain the grant.

European public health funding: An alternative approach discussed was to seek funding based on improving public health literacy and information dissemination, rather than a pure research focus.

- **The EU4Health program** focuses on the implementation of science for public health, which was seen as a good fit for the MUMS project. The program typically requires co-financing, with the EU providing up to 60% of the funding. For projects involving participants from Central and Eastern European countries, the EU's contribution can be increased to up to 80% of the funding. The EU4Health program was discussed as a potential source of funding for a medium-term period, with the suggestion that it could provide funding for 3-4 years.
- **Call to action:** An internal team to examine the grant funding opportunities, call topics and dates to agree on a strategy for a proposal, or seek out and join a consortium in development.

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European-level funding opportunities

"There are two other medicines-related European projects that are now starting to think about whether they might work together towards a future funding call.

MUMS would fit very nicely in that as a triangle of complementary areas, ...but you know, it will take at least a year or 18 months to get a call topic published. Then you have a grant proposal window followed by the time to negotiate before they kick off and the grant comes in. So, we're looking at three years from now, probably before the first bank transfer arises."

"The EU4Health...it needs at least three, four European countries, to work together. And if we have national patient organizations, it's another two or three plus points in every funding and grant. So, it's a really good idea, and it's quite quick."

"EU4Health as a funding program...focusing a lot now on implementation of science. It's also focusing a lot on prevention. And normally, it has to be co-financed to 40%, but it can be in kind. But the great thing here is that we've got really dynamic groups from Central & Eastern Europe, so we could get potentially up to 80%."

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National-level funding opportunities

- **Complementing European-level funding with national-level sources for the long-term sustainability and successful implementation of the MUMS project at the local level were discussed.**
- **Poland:** A participant representing Poland mentioned that there are funding sources available in the country for academic projects that focus on the social responsibility of science and the implementation of science for daily routine use. This could be a potential fit for the MUMS project, as it aligns with the project's goals of translating scientific knowledge into practical, everyday use for pregnant women. The participant also committed to following up on this and investigating when the next call for funding in this area might be, with the intention of exploring a potential application.
- **Romania:** A participant representing Romania mentioned that their organization could support the ongoing technical costs, such as website domain and hosting, for the MUMS project once it is up and running. This could encourage national stakeholders to take accountability and empower them in the long-term sustainability of the MUMS project
- **Funding for national-level pilots:** Similar national-level funding opportunities might exist in other countries represented, such as the Netherlands and the Czechia.
- **Call to action:** MUMS project team to engage with all the national participants to better understand the funding possibilities in their respective countries and to coordinate efforts to secure this type of support.

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National-level funding opportunities

"I would also assume, once the project is up, the cost for maintaining the project and hosting the website. These are not big costs...and they can be assumed by national parties long-term. My organization would have no problem supporting these costs once the project is up and running."

"From the Polish perspective, we have the funds for academics, not for the research, but for the projects that deal with the social responsibility of science..it is the project for implementing the science for daily routine use. So, I think that this project fits well in this call."

Third-party and philanthropic sources

- **Philanthropic foundations:** The Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation was discussed as a potential source of funding, given their focus on global health and women's health initiatives. The Bosch Foundation was also highlighted as a particularly promising philanthropic funding source, as they have previously funded projects related to women's health and patient empowerment.
- **Professional associations:** Engaging with healthcare professionals at congresses and professional societies such as the International Urogynaecology Association (IUGA) could be seen as an opportunity to foster collaboration and explore any funding opportunities.
- **Crowdfunding:** One participant mentioned crowdfunding as a potential source, especially considering the implications of the project for public health.
- **Engaging with the European Commission:** Gaining access to the right parliamentarians and key people within the new European Commission could be explored, although this may be more suitable for the long term.

Third-party and philanthropic sources

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"The IUGA and the European Gynaecological Congresses...I cannot see why it would not be a good idea to approach them and to have an initial chat to see if there's any common ground with the scientific society, so the HCPs and nurses and, midwives, etc and just take it from there."

These days, there are many other different types of funding streams. I'm thinking of Life Sciences, women's health, Bill Gates, I think perhaps it might not be a bad idea to look into those possibilities that may not have been looked into before."

The Bosch Foundation. Is committed to women's health and has funded some really good stuff in the past, not large amounts of money, but for example, a few years ago, they funded an entire campaign on patient empowerment, lasting 18 months, and it was enough to get things going beyond Germany, it was pan-European."

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Long-term self-sustainability of MUMS

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- **Revenue from e-learning modules:** As part of Work Package 5, an e-learning module has been developed and is being piloted in Ireland. This e-learning module could potentially generate revenue if universities and other organizations become willing to pay for access and accreditation. However, the group acknowledged that the revenue generated may not be sufficient to fully sustain the MUMS project on its own.
- **Advertising:** Alternative funding streams, such as advertisements on the MUMS platform, could generate revenue. The group discussed the potential for some form of advertising, as long as it was not for individual drug products, which would be problematic.

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Long-term self-sustainability of MUMS

"The e-learning module has been generated, and it's now piloted at Irish University and being accredited at the European level. And I think in the end, we see that there's a money generating option there, so we want to be partially for free, but maybe that's for universities that they pay to use the module and get accreditation. So, there's a sustainable model there, but it's not clear how much it will generate, and if it's if that money that it will generate will be sufficient to keep the e-learning going, but it will not be generating that much money, I think, to sustain MUMS"

I think to explore those alternative funding streams is quite critical, including advertisement or micropayments or payments by professional associations."

"Because of governmental changes, I think it's important for each teratology Information Service to look at their funding. We are funded to keep the knowledge bank up to date, and don't generate any money ourselves, but we are looking into deals with a pharmacist system that they would be wanting to pay for the knowledge that we generate for them that they use. But it's quite tricky and long discussions. So I think there are opportunities there, but they're not so easy".

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Discussions around industry funding

- While industry funding was proposed as a potential source, there are significant risks and conflicts of interest with the MUMS project's objectives and long-term sustainability.
- **Funding from national-level industry associations:** A participant representing Romania suggested that approaching national federations of drug makers and distributors could be a potential way to secure funding for the MUMS project. The rationale was that these industry associations represent all the pharmaceutical companies in a country rather than individual companies, which could help avoid some conflicts of interest. This association is currently planning its budgets for the next year, and this could be explored as an immediate source.
- **Generic/OTC drug makers associations:** Approaching generic/OTC drug makers associations, rather than individual companies, was mentioned as a potential funding avenue worth exploring.
- **Risks associated with industry funding:** Many participants expressed concerns about accepting industry funding for the MUMS project. They noted that pharmaceutical companies, even through industry associations, are generally not allowed to fund projects that deviate from the information provided in the Summary of Product Characteristics (SmPC) for their products. There was also a strong consensus that accepting industry funding could compromise the independence and credibility of the MUMS project.

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Discussions around industry funding

Key action points from the workshop

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Meeting report

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